

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D2.5

Biomass supply chain assessment report

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D2.5 Biomass supply chain assessment report		
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Publishable summary

The supply chain assessment has been prepared in the frame of the HORIZON 2020 funded project "Smart and flexible heat and power from biomass derived liquids for small-scale CHP application". This study aims to improve the understanding of chosen biomass supply chains parallel to other project tasks in order to analyze realistic Smart CHP project cases and contribute to further development of the CHP systems and by so contributing to increasing performance of renewable technology.

The EU long Term Strategy aims to climate-neutrality by 2050, i.e. aiming to become an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. The European Green Deal, sets EU-wide targets and policy objectives for the period up to 2030, which translate into: at least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels), at least 32% share for renewable energy, and at least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

EU Funded SmartCHP project is a contribution to climate neutrality, its scope being the development of a highly flexible small-scale Combined Heat and Power (CHP) system (0.1 - 1 MWe), fueled with Fast Pyrolysis Bio Oil (FPBO) produced from different types of lignocellulosic biomass residues.

SmartCHP addresses targets set by the Green-Deal and the EU "Vision to 2050" through (a) its contribution to the improvement of Energy Efficiency, as CHP is by definition an efficient technology, thus (b) contributing to the reduction of GHG emissions per unit of energy used, whereas (c) it uses at the same time a RE fuel -Fast Pyrolysis Bio-oil -for the production of which, biomass is the source.

The supply chain assessment is based on selection of 5 focus countries within the course of SmartCHP deliverables. The countries selected are: Sweden, the Netherlands, Croatia, Romania and Greece. The feedstock selected for each country respectively: Softwood residues, export of oil scenario (not explored in this deliverable), Miscanthus, Corn stover and olive kernel wood. The report analyses the availability, price, logistics, suitability and sustainability of individual feedstock based on its VPL (virtual plant location) model that is being used to achieve tangible and close to reality scenarios.

List of Abbreviations

AR	Agricultural residues
CHP	Combined Heat & Power
EC	European Commission
FPBO	Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil
FR	Forestry residues
OWR	Organic Waste Residues (food and feed processing side streams)
RES	Renewable Energy System
VPL	Virtual plant location

References

Beeco project – beeco.hr

Nike Krajnc, Tina Jemec, Todora Rogelja, Diego Mattioli, Senta Schmatzberger, Anthony Luttmann, Teo Hrvoje Oršanič, Mojca Kunst, Pal Kezdy, Laudati Michele, Antonio

Falcone, Rosy Cannata, Domenico Cerinara, Stavros Kechagioglou, Christos Karachristos,

Spyros Galatsidas, Nikolaos Gounaris, Garyfallos Arabatzis, 2015, Bioeuroparks.eu – Guidelines. Steps in setting up wood biomass production chains in protected areas

https://www.bioeuroparks.eu/files/bioeuroparks/project-files/4_1_guidelines_en_final.pdf

Danje S. 2011, Fast pyrolysis of corn residues for energy production, Thesis, Stellenbosch University

Eurostat – statistical reports for biomass

Esteban, L. S., & Carrasco, J. E., 2011. Biomass resources and costs: Assessment in different EU countries

Fischer G. et al 2007, Assessment of biomass potentials for biofuel feedstock production in Europe: Methodology and results, Refuel project

Beatriz Gómez-Muñoz, David J. Hatch, Roland Bol and Roberto García-Ruiz 2012 The Compost of Olive Mill Pomace: From a Waste to a Resource - Environmental Benefits of Its Application in Olive Oil Groves, Sustainable development

Hartmann H. T. and Bougas P. G. 2016, Olive Production in Greece, Springer publications

Irena.org – Swedish approach to sustainable wood use

Iqbal Y. Et al. 2016 Maximising the yield of biomass from residues of agricultural crops and biomass from forestry

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Study on impacts on resource efficiency of future EU demand for bioenergy, task 1 report, 2014

JRC, Biomass flows, dataM – Biomass estimates (v3): a new database to quantify biomass availability in the European Union

Kalarchakis I, 2013 Attribute analysis and quality assessment of extra virgin olive oil produced in Sitia, Crete, Greece; Cranfield University; Department of Nutrition & Dietetics of the Technological Educational Institute of Crete

Kehbila A. T., 2010, EVALUATION OF PRIMARY WOOD PROCESSING RESIDUES FOR BIOENERGY IN BRITISH COLUMBIA, University of British Columbia, Masters thesis, <https://open.library.ubc.ca/media/stream/pdf/24/1.0071189/1> accessed 12/07/2022

Kumar, A., Adamopoulos, S., Jones, D. et al. Forest Biomass Availability and Utilization Potential in Sweden: A Review. Waste Biomass Valor 12, 65–80 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-020-00947-0>

Lewandowski, I., Clifton-Brown, J., Trindade, L. M., van der Linden, G. C., Schwarz, K. U., Müller-Sämann, K., ... & Farrar, K., 2016. Progress on optimizing Miscanthus biomass production for the European bioeconomy: Results of the EU FP7 project OPTIMISC. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 7.

Lewandowski, I., Clifton-Brown, J., Scurlock J. M. O., Huisman W., 2000, *Miscanthus: European experience with a novel energy crop*, Elsevier, Biomass and Bioenergy 19 (2000) 209–227

<https://mapchart.net/europe-nuts3.html>

Menedez J. A. et al, 2018, Report on the availability of Biomass Sources in Spain: vineyards and olive groves

Miscanthus potential - <http://eng.beeco.hr/miscanthus-potential/>

Miscanthus group et. al, 2019, Commercial cultivation of *Miscanthus giganteus* for planting material & biomass production in Croatia.

MoRE project – Market of olive residues for energy, 2008, Final publishable report

MoRE project – Market of olive residues for energy, 2008, Joint report on best practices

Pitman R., Wood Ash use in forestry. A Review of the Environmental Impacts. Governmental Forest research

Polak V. K. et al, 2017 The potential feedstock for the production of advanced biofuels in Croatia, INA Presentation Athens, Greece.

Royal Swedish Academy of Agriculture and Forestry, 2015, Forests and Forestry in Sweden.

Shinners, Kevin & Binversie, Ben & Savoie, Philippe. (2020). HARVEST AND STORAGE OF WET AND DRY CORN STOVER AS A BIOMASS FEEDSTOCK. 10.13031/2013.15403.

Soare and Dobre, 2016 Changes and trends in corn production in Romania. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development* Vol. 16, Issue 1

Thorenz A. et al 2018, Assessment of agroforestry residue potentials for the bioeconomy in the European Union

Voca N. et al, 2019, Revitalization of abandoned agricultural lands in Croatia using the energy crop *Miscanthus X Giganteus*, *Journal on Processing and Energy in Agriculture* 23, 3

Vourdoubas J., TEI of Crete, Department of Natural Resources and Environment, Possibilities of using olive kernel wood for power generation on Crete – Greece

Vourdoubas, J., 2017, Possibilities of Energy Generation from Olive Tree Residues, by-products and Waste in Crete, Greece. *Journal of Agricultural Studies* 5(4):110 DOI: 10.5296/jas.v5i4.12114

YORGUN, S. (2003). Fixed-Bed Pyrolysis of Miscanthus x giganteus: Product Yields and Bio-Oil Characterization. *Energy Sources*, 25(8), 779–790. doi:10.1080/00908310390207828

Wendt L et al, 2018 Techno-Economic Assessment of a Chopped Feedstock Logistics Supply Chain for Corn Stover, Bioenergy and fuels 2018, volume 6, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2018.00090>

Wietchel L. et al, 2019, Spatially explicit forecast of feedstock potentials for second generation bioconversion industry from the EU agricultural sector until the year 2030

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1. The project

1.1 Project summary

The objective of SmartCHP is the realization of a cost-effective and flexible energy system by using a liquid bio- energy carrier to fuel an efficient diesel-engine based CHP. It will develop a smart and flexible, small-scale CHP unit (100-1,000 kWe) fueled with fast pyrolysis bio-oil originating from different types of biomasses and/or residues. Fast pyrolysis converts biomass into a uniform liquid intermediate called FPBO, and the process is characterized by a high feedstock flexibility. Nowadays, FPBO is produced on commercial scale in Europe. For small scale biomass CHP systems, a standardized fuel enabling optimization of the conversion units and thus creating a cost competitive value chain, is highly preferred. Moreover, to achieve high resource efficiencies at all times a highly flexible ratio between heat and power generation is desired. A smart, demand driven unit should be capable of dealing with the fluctuating energy demand and/or varying availability of wind/solar power. The SmartCHP system combines a FPBO fueled engine and flue gas boiler to produce electricity and heat at a high efficiency over the whole load range. A dedicated flue gas treatment guarantees low emissions. Moreover, a wide, adjustable heat-to-power ratio is covered, which enables to respond directly to actual energy demands. The final result of SmartCHP is an integrated system consisting of an engine, boiler and flue gas treatment system adapted and optimized to run on FPBO (TRL 5). A real-time, predictive, dynamic model will be developed to find the optimal operation point at all energy demands. Techno-economic, socio-economic and environmental assessments will be performed to identify real market opportunities. The SmartCHP unit will be based on standard diesel engines, and specific investment costs are expected to be around 1,200 Eur/kWe; an electricity price below 0.10 Eur/kWh is realistic. Several case studies will be presented to illustrate the opportunities throughout Europe.

1.2 Content of the deliverable report

The public report is part of SmartCHP project deliverables, where data and assessment of the biomass supply chain from resource to pyrolysis plant for the selected biomass feedstocks within the project is presented.

1.3 DOW

Task 2.3: Assessment of the biomass supply chain from resource to the pyrolysis plant (CAPAX, M18 – M44)

The biomass supply chain from the resource to the fast pyrolysis plant including collection, pre-treatment and logistics will be evaluated from a techno-economic viewpoint, i.e. assessment of required equipment, needed labour, material, energy use, other costs leading to insight in technical feasibility, CAPEX and OPEX and related risks of the different supply chains. The base-case is a standard fast pyrolysis plant with a capacity of 40,000 metric tons (dry) of biomass input per year. Distribution of the FPBO from the plant to multiple SmartCHP end-users is covered in WP6. This subtask will be carried out in close cooperation with WP5 (environmental assessment) and WP6 (SmartCHP Market and business assessment). The assessment will be aligned with the cases selected in WP6.

1.4 Scope

This deliverable covers the focus of biomass importance in the production of FPBO fueled by smart CHP systems.

1.5 Goal and purpose

The goal of this deliverable is to further evaluate feedstocks as part of the supply chain of FPBO production. Three feedstock categories as described in the task description will be evaluated covering European regions where a significant potential of smart CHP has been found as per task 2.1, deliverable 2.1.

1.6 Approach

The approach of this deliverable is to analyze different data on a local base for each feedstock case. The deliverable will be reached by presenting and analyzing the availability, price, logistics, suitability and sustainability of individual feedstock. A virtual pyrolysis plant location (VPL) model is used to achieve tangible and close to reality scenarios.

2. Introduction

2.1 Project Overview

SmartCHP project conducted biomass feedstock analyses based on a number of variables in order to choose most prominent biomass choices for the project. The primary parameter of the choices was based on suitability first. In close cooperation with other work within the project (WP6), European countries were evaluated based on availability, geographical spread (per EU region) and other parameters, including close cooperation with WP6. In order to come to the most feasible cases, the location and feedstock choices are based on the "virtual plant location" strategy, whereas:

The pyrolysis plants are defined to stand "virtually" in a specific region in order to help to evaluate the biomass resources in tangible and clear scenarios for each virtual location selection.

Table 1: Detailed feedstock parameters that helped to conclude the best feedstock choices within the SmartCHP project. . FR – Forest residue, AR – Agricultural residue, OWR – Organic waste; DLBC – Dedicated lignocellulosic biomass crop.

Country	Feedstock	Category	Selected Region(s)	Availability (t)	VPL location	Industrial symbiosis	Logistical advantages	Price guide ³
Sweden	Softwood	FR	Vastra Gotland, Halland	1.2 mil ⁵ and 268 000 ⁵	Boras	No	Proximity to port, good road access	50-150 ⁴
The Netherlands	Oil Import ¹	FR	-		-	-	-	-
Croatia	Miscanthus	DLBC	Sisak-Moslavina, Karlovac	63 000 and 53 000	Sisak	Yes, oil refinery complex	Good road access	50-90
Romania	Corn stover	AR	Muntenia (Ialomita, Braila, Burzau) Dobrogea (Constanta)	75 000	Slobozia	Yes, corn processing factory	Proximity to port, Good road access	42-70
Greece	Olive KR ²	OWR	Crete	62 000	Kapariana	No	Proximity to port and airport, good road access	50-60

1 This scenario considers oil import from Sweden into the Netherlands.

2 Olive Kernel wood – pomace and pits from processing

3 Expressed in Eur, the range includes local and delivered price, non densified

4 Higher price range includes densified feedstock price (specifically pellets)

The framework of previous work of the deliverables is outlined in Table 1. Each feedstock and its selected region choice are based on availability, price, logistics, suitability and sustainability parameters. Other parameters were also considered (not outlined in the table), for e.g. RED II emission reduction calculations, CO₂ targets, local energy context, CHP production, etc. Detailed data and reasoning of the choices is confidential to the project, however the outline gives a great overview and chosen VPL locations will be used within this report to deliver as closely accurate supply chain analysis for each targeted feedstock. A visual representation

of the regions and VPL positioning is displayed in Figure 1. Additionally, the findings of this deliverable will be based and calculated on the standard pyrolysis oil plant capacity, which is 5t/h plant that needs 44 ktons of dry biomass per year.

Selected EU Countries

- The Netherlands (export scenario)
- Sweden
- Croatia
- Romania
- Greece
- Local sourcing regions
- VPL position

Figure 1: Visual Virtual location positioning of targeted pyrolysis plant production points for SmartCHP systems.

In the case of the Netherlands scenario, the feedstock availability is not applicable. This scenario will be looked into in WP6. An overview of availability for specified feedstocks was analyzed (D2.1) for each country and is summarized in Table 2.

Overall, as detailed in previous report, there is sufficient quantities of dedicated biomass available in each selected country. Romania has 2.29 mil. ton corn stover residue based on theoretical yield potential. Main competitive markets for this feedstock are in the feed and fodder section as well as use for ethanol production. In Sweden, the production capacity of softwood is around 70 mil. m³, where the feedstock can be used for various applications ranging from energy to pulp and paper, panel wood, timber and mulching markets. In Greece, at least 82000 tons of kernels are available based on olive production capacity. To this day, olive kernels are considered a good source of fuel locally due to its high heating value. Additionally, it can also be used as abrasive materials. New applications such as additives to animal feed and to fertilizers are emerging. In Croatia, the total amount of unused land available is 750 000 ha. Miscanthus is currently being grown mainly for energy uses within Europe. The following sections will present each country availability data in more detail.

Table 2: Chosen feedstocks and their availability potential, including competition.

Country	Feedstock	Availability potential (production capacity)	Competitive markets
Netherlands	-	-	-
Romania	Corn stover	14.3 mil. t corn, of which 2.29 mil. t stover (based on 16% theoretical yield potential) *	Feed, fodder, ethanol production
Sweden	Softwood	73 mil. m ³ *	Timber, Pulp & paper, panel wood, mulching, energy
Greece	Olive kernels	2.720488 t Olives, of which 81615 t kernels (based on 3% theoretical yield potential) *	Fuel (high heating value), abrasive materials, fertilizers, animal feeds
Croatia	Miscanthus	750 000 ha unused land **	Biofuel, other energy and non-energy uses (e.g. mulching, isolation)

* 2017 data

** 2019 data

2.2 Feedstock positioning in relation to the supply chain

The supply chain analysis will include detailed analysis of how the feedstock is processed in the sourcing region detailed in Table 3. Common growing, harvesting and processing models will be looked at in the view of the Smart CHP project. This will allow to understand the origin of the feedstock, common regional practices, where the supply and demand flow originates and what are the competitive uses for the feedstocks; what are the challenges obtaining the feedstock in the required characteristics for CHP process, what are storage, transport and pre-treatment requirements and as a result will allow to understand what are the overall advantages, costs and challenges to obtain the feedstock. Table 3 presents a simplified summary of selected feedstock categories, sourcing region and virtual plant location (VPL) positioning.

Table 3: Summary of feedstock and country choices based on the findings within the project deliverables.

Chapter	Country (VPL location)	Category	Feedstock	Sourcing Region
3.	Sweden (Boras)	Forest residues	Softwood residues (shavings, dust)	Vastra Gotland, Halland
-	Netherlands	Pyrolysis oil import scenario	- (import from Sweden)	-
6.	Greece (Kapariana village, Heraklion)	Organic waste residues	Olive kernel wood	Crete
4.	Croatia (Sisak)	Dedicated Lignocellulosic biomass crop	Miscanthus	Sisak-Moslavina, Karlovac
5.	Romania (slobozia)	Agricultural residues	Corn stover	Muntenia (Ialomita, Braila, Burzau), Dobrogea (Constanta)

The biomass supply chain from the resource to the fast pyrolysis plant including collection, pre-treatment and logistics will be evaluated from a techno-economic viewpoint, i.e. assessment of required equipment, needed labour, material, energy use, other costs leading to insight in technical feasibility, CAPEX and OPEX and related risks of the different supply chains.

3. Supply chain of Swedish softwood residues

Softwood residues originate from by-products and residues from the wood processing industry. Forest biomass (1) can be derived from logging operations, forest thinning or improvement projects. Additionally, plantations (termed as Swedish forestry model, rotated every 20 years) constitute about 60% of the forestry model in Sweden, therefore this model will be covered under forest biomass derivatives since biomass is collected in the same manner as from the forest once the plantation is old enough. Round wood

Figure 2: A scheme representing forestry softwood wood flow in Sweden, including stem, pulpwood and forest residues. Smart CHP project looks at utilizing residual material from all three categories. Adapted from Kumar A. et al 2020

that is harvested in all forestry activities are used in sawmills (2), where a number of by-products and final products are produced within the primary and secondary processes. Pulp and paper industries are supplied wood chips and shavings by sawmills, while logs come directly from log terminal. Table 4 displays a summary of all residue types from different operations, from forestry to sawmill and further. In this chapter, a detailed description of (1) forest residue and (2) sawmill residue supply chain is covered in more detail, since this is the most common source of softwood residue origin relevant to SmartCHP processes.

Table 4: Types of wood residues from different operations. Adapted from Kizha 2008.

Source of residue	Type of residue
Forest operations	Branches, needles, stumps, leaves, roots, low-grade and decayed wood, slash and sawdust
Sawmilling and planning	Bark, sawdust, trimmings, split wood, planer shavings
Plywood and particle production	Bark, core, sawdust, panel trim, veneer clippings and waste, screening fines, sawdust, sander dust
Secondary forest product industry	Bark, wood chips, shavings, sawdust, etc.

FAO 1993 and Parikka 2004

Figure 3: Overview of biomass and energy flows from Swedish forest. Adapted from IRENA (Swedish forest bioenergy).

3.1 Availability of softwood residues

Sweden is one of the most densely forested countries in Europe. Out of total 40.8 million ha of land, 70% is covered with trees. 57% of the land is dedicated to a productive forest land, where the majority of trees are comprising spruce (40%), pine (38%) and birch (12%) (Figure 4). In 2019, Sweden was the highest round wood producing country with 73 million cubic meters of stemwood production. Pulp industry is considered as the main consumer of wood followed by the sawmill industry. On average, out of all forestry operations around 22.6 million m³ of forest residue is available throughout the country (14.9% of total supply). Moreover, sawmill by-products comprise 18.4 million m³ of wood chips, slabs, edgings, trimmings and sawdust particles. Overall, total availability of residual material both from forest and sawmill activities is 41 million cubic meters throughout the country.

Figure 4: Swedish land use and forest tree distribution. Adapted from FISE - Forest Information System for Europe and EUROPA databases (2020).

Sweden is divided into 4 regions – Gotaland, and Svealand makes up the southern part of Sweden, while the northern part is Norrland, divided into south and north (Sodra and Norra) respectively (Figure 5b). Overall, Sweden’s harvesting capacities have been steadily increasing each year due to demand, better forest maintenance, reforestation movement, and other reasons. Compared to all regions, Gotaland has the highest wood production capacity where each year the quantity has been steadily increasing compared to the other regions, where the growth was somewhat slower or more cyclical (National Swedish statistics). In 2017, 34.2 million m³ of wood was available in Gotaland, while Svealand had 28.3 million m³, Norra Norrland had 12.2 million m³ and Sodra Norrland 9.4 million m³. Within the regions, counties that have the highest production capacity are: Vastra gotland (Gotaland) 8.2 million m³, Vasternorrlands (Norra Norlands, part of Angermanland province) 9 million m³ and Jamtlands (Sodra Norrland) 7.8 million m³ (Figure 6). These figures are for total wood harvest.

Although sufficient quantities of forest residue would be available in specific counties within all regions, southern Sweden will be further considered from logistical point of view and keeping in mind the export scenario. The aim is to use one VPL that is able to supply locally and export to the Netherlands. There are 5 logistical points available throughout the country in the areas of Stockholm, Norrkoping, Gothenburg, Helsingborg and Malmo. Considering the distance to port at 100-150 km from a potential plant location, the following counties could be considered:

- Port of Stockholm – Uppsalla (Svealand Region);
- Port of Gothenburg – Halland, Vastra Gotlands (Alvsborg, Skaraborg counties);
- Port of Norrkoping – Ostergotland;
- Port of Helsingborg – Halland, Skane (Kristianstad, Malmohus counties);
- Port of Malmo – Skane (Kristianstad, Malmohus counties).

In Uppsalla (Svealand Region), the potential wood residue production capacity is around 462 thousand m³ (total wood production capacity 3.1 million m³). Meanwhile, Gotaland wood residue potential is 5.1 million m³, of which 1.2 million m³ is potentially available in Vastra Gotland, 268 thousand m³ in Halland, 581 thousand m³ in Ostergotland and 417 thousand m³ in Skane counties respectively. Considering that an annual pyrolysis oil feedstock use is on average 37 500 – 42 500 tones of feedstock, all of these counties would have sufficient amounts available.

Källa: Skogsstyrelsen

Figure 5: a) Sweden and its provinces and regions – Götaland (blue), Svealand (light yellow) and Norrland, which is also divided to Södra (southern) Norrland (golden yellow) and Norra (northern) Norrland (green); b) Harvested volume, million m³ by region, Sweden; c) Area (ha) notification of harvesting and application for harvesting by region.

Figure 6: Gross felling (1000 m³) by region (marked in color) and county.

3.1.1 Swedish VPL positioning

The positioning of VPL in Sweden has been concluded to be most efficient in the proximity of Gothenburg port due to export to the Netherlands scenario. This port is situated at closest proximity to the Netherlands.

Figure 7: Logistical advantages of positioning VPL in the municipality of Borås, Västra Götaland (red outlined area). Sawmill examples pointed out on average do not exceed 150 km distance from the VPL location. The port is also within good logistical reach for the oil export case scenario to the Netherlands. The routes are shown only for visualization purposes in order to locate VPL positioning and some available sawmill examples. The availability of forest residues is all round depending on the variable harvesting locations at a time.

For this, Halland and Vastra Gotlands (Alvsborg, Skaraborg counties) are suitable regions in order to reach sustainable distance requirements of up to 150 km to the port (Figure 7). In these regions, plenty of sawmill activities are scattered around as well as regular forest maintenance activities take place, therefore plenty of wood residues available. By positioning the VPL in the municipality of Boras, good road and rail access is available to the port of Gothenburg as well as many wood supply sites within the reach within both regions.

For instance, in Vastra Gotlands there are a number of sawmills available, such as Vida Borgstena, Sodra wood, etc.. Meanwhile, in Halland region - Bjenareds Sagverk, Fegens Hyvleri, Fegens Sagverk, Derome timber (total production capacity 600,000 cubic metres), etc. To calculate theoretical residue potential, we have used UNECE forest product conversion guide, where 7% of shavings are accounted for shavings/sawdust. This would mean that theoretically at least 42 000 cubic meters of shavings are available within Derome timber alone. Data for other sawmill capacities was not available. Overall, looking at availability within the area as described earlier in section 3.1 , placing a VPL in Boras municipality gives a good advantage logistically.

3.2 Forestry residue harvest and processing

3.2.1 Origin

Forest biomass can originate from various different sources, for example logging operations, improvement projects or forest thinning operations. Feedstock is harvested from top parts of the trees or limbs and may include various processes, such as felling, piling, bundling, forwarding, chipping and trucking. As a common practice, a typical forest harvesting includes round wood products that are cut as whole trees and piled. They can be then forwarded by a buncher or a feller, where they are debarked and de-limbed. Most round wood products go to pulp and paper or timber markets. Around 13% of total softwood volume makes up logging residues, of which mostly constitute tops and limbs. A mechanical bundler can be used to bundle the limbs after delimiting. Trunk size bundles are made for the efficient hauling and/or storage. An integrated bundler system is available in some fellers or bunchers. Further size reduction (for e.g. chipping, pelletizing, briquetting) can be applied at a biorefinery, satellite pre-processing facility or industrial bioenergy power plant.

Supply chains for logging residues (or log chips)

Figure 8: A representation of a typical acquisition of logging residues from forestry operations. Adapted from VTT, Wood energy technology programme.

3.2.2 Harvest and processing

The residue is left in the forest in order to enhance soil nutrient cycle dynamics or can be harvested as biomass. Figure 8 displays a diagram representing of the four (4) main supply chains of harvesting forestry residues. Slash from final fellings, slash and small trees from thinnings and clean-ups or non-merchandised wood are used:

1. Terrain chipping

Highly mobile chipper moves in the terrain on the strip roads with a tippable chip container. The biomass is then transferred with a grapple loader to the feeder. Chipped material is hauled to the road side and tipped into a truck container.

2. Chipping at a landing (roadside chipping)

The biomass is hauled by independently operated forwarders to the landing and bunched into piles. Farm-tractor driven chippers or heavy truck mounted chippers\crushers are used. The chips can be directly blown into a container that hauls the load to the plant.

3. Terminal chipping (Biomass platform)

The system is similar to chipping at a landing, except the biomass is hauled to the terminal for the size reduction and then transported to the plant in the form of chips. A terminal is a tool to control procurement and store biomass non-pulverized. The biomass is processed based on the demand and forest working conditions.

4. Chipping at a plant

Heavy stationary crushers are used that are suitable for pulverizing all types of biomass. Truck transportation of biomass in this case is executed in the form of loose logging residues, pieces of wood or whole trees. Low bulk density can be

Table 5: Summary of forestry chips supply chain. Source – Indufor, EU27, VTT

Supply chain	Raw materials	Location			
		Forest stand	Roadside	Terminal	Plant reception
Terrain chipping	Logging residues	Highly mobile chipper moves in the terrain on the strip roads with a tippable chip container. The biomass is transferred with a grapple loader to the feeder	Chipped material is hauled to the roadside and loaded into a truck container	-	Forest chips arrive at the plant
Roadside chipping	Tops and branches Small size stemwood Stumps	Wood is forwarded to the roadside	Wood is chipped with mobile chipper to a truck	-	Forest chips arrive at the plant
Terminal chipping	Tops and branches Small size stemwood Stumps Pulpwood logs Defected sawlogs	Wood is forwarded to the roadside	Wood is loaded on a truck and transported to a terminal	Wood is chipped with a large stationary or mobile chipper and loaded onto a truck	Forest chips arrive at the plant
Plant chipping	Tops and branches Small size stemwood Stumps Pulpwood logs Defect sawlogs	Wood is forwarded to the roadside. Tops and branches or small diameter stemwood can be bundled with purpose-built machine	Bulk wood or bundles are loaded on to a truck and transported to a terminal	-	Bulk wood or bundles are chipped at the plant

addressed by baling into 70 cm x 3 m long bales that are transported to the roadside with a conventional forwarder.

Chipping of residues improves storage and transport; however, it can lead to higher cost of harvesting operations. The major advantage of chipping is size reduction and homogeneity (uniformity) that can be crucial for the end users (for example, energy market, pyrolysis process). Wood chipping is implemented by using mechanical force process, including a set of knives, hammers or auger. An engine powers the flywheel which is mounted with the knives. Local processing of biomass allows the production of uniform particle sizes, makes the moisture content more consistent and improves the flowability of the material. Consequently, downstream biomass transport and logistics allow a diverse range of biomass processing under common equipment with economy of scale and system level efficiencies.

3.3 Sawmill residue processing

3.3.1 Origin

Round wood harvested in the forestry activities can be used in a sawmill, where a number of by-products and final products can be produced, when timber is being processed. In the sawmill, the goal is to produce boards and planks based on customer requirements. The quality of the raw material therefore is of importance. During the process of the board and plank production, by-products such as bark, chips, sawdust and slabs are produced (Figure 9). Production depends and varies on sawing technology, where the process can be fully automated and computerized. Typically, softwood is processed in separated softwood sawmills.

Figure 9: A representation of a typical sawmill processing activities. Adapted from European wood organization.

Bark is the outer part of the logs that is recovered from the debarking process. It makes up 9-15% of the log, and is commonly used in mulching and as a soil amendment. Bark can pose difficulties in utilization, because it contains a lot of contaminants such as soil from harvesting operations. As utilization technologies improve, more and more bark is chemically extracted for its tannins, resins, dyes and organic compounds.

Sawdust is made when a log is cut to make lumber. Sawdust is fairly uniform in particle size, but has a high moisture content. Upon drying, sawdust can be used in combustion, gasification and pyrolysis processes or for fiber composite manufacturing. Sawdust has specific characteristics that make it desirable in abrasives, bedding, insulation and packaging.

Figure 10: Different softwood side streams of sawmill operations: Bark, Sawdust, Cellulose chips, Uneven chips, planing chips. Adapted from Kumar et al 2020

The side streams originating in the sawmill operation can be measured by the industry standard (such as SCAN-CM 40-94). The chips pass through the mesh wires and are fractionated and classified by size and weight. The material is fractionated as: i) oversize (above 45mm); ii) overthick (above 8mm); iii) accept (above 7mm); iv) pin chips (above 3mm); and v) fines (below 3mm).

3.4 Production chain

In a traditional timber harvesting chain, wood chips are produced from three primary forest biomasses:

1. Slash – residues harvested from final felling, such as small trees, tops of branches, bushes and thinning.
2. Stumps – from final felling.
3. Discarded wood – unsuitable for industry, discarded species, rotten or sprouted stems.

The chain begins with cutting trees, delimiting and crosscutting with a wheeled harvester (140 kw). Timber is collected and skidded to the road of the forest with a forwarder of a capacity of 12 t.

The slash is collected in a separate operation with a press collector or bundler and usually stacked at the roadside to dry from ~50% to ~30% mc. The dried slash can be chipped with a mobile chipper straight into a transport truck with a loading device. It can be either separate from the truck or mounted on it. Similarly, stumps are up-rooted with a digger and piled to dry next to the slash. Stumps are usually crushed to avoid damage to the chipper from possible contaminants such as stones and soil.

Truckload is delivered to the plant with the walking floor truck is weighted and samples are taken to determine the MC and the cost of the material is considered based on the heating value.

3.5 Costs within softwood residue harvesting

It is important that woody biomass use for energy is economically viable. The main cost factors are similar of wood for energy and timber harvesting chain. The main difference is that energy dedicated biomass has lower harvesting yields, lower quality and lower market price compared to wood dedicated to industrial use. In this section we will discuss the cost of i) forestry chips, that are primary wood energy source derived from timber harvesting chain residues; and ii) wood pellets, that are made from industrial by-products as a secondary wood energy source, such as sawmill activities.

3.5.1 Forestry chips

Harvesting methods, conditions of the terrain, tree size, density, productivity, etc have all direct impact on the cost of forestry chip production costs. Harvesting tops and branches has lower cost, because the tree size is smaller, therefore lower accumulated volume per machine working hour. Harvesting price also depends on fuel and labor costs as well as infrastructure, machinery and energy infrastructure.

Centralized chipping operations with chip storage at the terminal is a cost-efficient option for large CHP plants. However, decentralized supply chain (e.g. roadside chipping) can be considered as a general supply chain for all size plants. In general, all Nordic supply chains are well established and all supply chains are efficiently used. Labor and fuel costs are among the highest within Europe (EU27). The

highest costs are attributed forestry chips from roundwood, while roadside operations have the lowest costs (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Supply costs Eur/MWh of various supply chains of forest chips in Sweden. Adapted from Laitila, J. et. al. 2010

Moisture content (mc) is the most important attribute when it comes to forestry chips. Higher mc affects storage, heating value, chipping and transport costs. Higher mc also means higher weight, comparable transport volume but higher fuel consumption for the truckloads. The CO₂ emissions impact becomes higher for the transport too. With proper drying of forestry chips within the supply chain, up to 33% savings for the supply chain costs and emissions have been estimated¹.

3.5.2 Pellets from sawmill activities

Wood pellet manufacturing is an integration to sawmill activities, where cheap by-products are refined and turned into value-added products. In the beginning, wood pelletizing was mainly integrated within the sawmill industry activities, but growing demands pushed it to emerge to independent pellet industry. Particularly in Sweden, wood-pellet mills use the industrial by-product resources from sawmills with efficient integration as a symbiotic industrial activity. The demand of wood pellets is increasing, however due to reduced sawmilling activities since 2007 the producers seek to use small diameter roundwood as a raw material for pellet making. Therefore, the pellet pricing

¹ International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, 2014

Figure 12: Industrial pellet production costs in Sweden. Source – Indufor

has been increasing as roundwood is a more expensive raw material and requires pre-investment to de-bark, chip and additional drying. When comparing pellets made from sawmill residues and roundwood, a 30% increase in production costs has been observed².

3.5.3 Transport

Different ways of transportation are possible for woody biomass. The majority of woody biomass is transported as woodchips. The average bulk density of fresh wood chips is around 250-300 kg/m³. On average, 25-28 tonnes fit in on a 90 m³ walking floor truck.

In Scandinavia, specifically Sweden woody biomass from softwood (slash) is often delivered to the end customer in bundles. The bales weigh between 400 and 850 kg depending on length, debri characteristics and moisture content. An average 24T truck loads with flatbed trucks can be achieved.

² Ihalainen and Sikanen (2010)

4. Supply chain of Croatian Miscanthus

4.1 Availability

Currently, Miscanthus is grown commercially only in a few European countries. Only about 20 000 ha of land is dedicated to Miscanthus within UK (10 000 ha), France (4000 ha), Germany (4000 ha), Switzerland (500 ha) and Poland (500 ha). Croatia is, however classified as one of the best territories for *Miscanthus x giganteus* cultivation. Primarily, Croatia has an ideal climate for this crop, but also more than 750 000 ha of unused agricultural land. Miscanthus is an ideal choice for this land because of its cold tolerance as well as the global trends (EU renewable energy directive targets) set out for natural energy sources. In addition, a Croatian National energy program supports better biomass energy utilization and it is expected that Miscanthus will bring numerous socio-economic benefits to the country.

Figure 13: a) Croatian land use by category; b) Croatian regions (in back) and potential counties for Miscanthus production (light blue name tags: Karlovac, Sisak-Moslavina, Lika-Senj;).

In Croatia, agricultural land covers 3.2 mil. ha of the country, of which around 1.5 mil. ha is arable land. Only 3.5% is used for vegetable growth (around 55 000 ha). As displayed in Figure 13 a and b, field crops and mixed farming are mainly residing in Slavonia (Northern east part), central Croatia and Kvarner regions. Table 6a shows data detailing land availability by county, where total abandoned land and used land (devoted to crops) is displayed by hectares. A lot of counties have abandoned agricultural land, but not all land is suitable for energy crops. For example, Osijek-Baranja and Vukovar Srijem are devoted to food crop production, while entire regions of Istria and Dalmatia are used for horticultural crops. Moreover, these regions do not have favorable weather conditions for Miscanthus. Based on a study that focused on using abandoned agricultural land in Croatia³,

³ Voca N. et al, 2019

the most favorable areas for dedicated lignocellulosic biomass crop production are counties of Sisak-Moslavina, Karlovac and Lika-senj (Figure 13b) because of its poor-quality soil and therefore low food-energy crop competition. Other parameters that directed to these counties were: reduced agricultural potential and satisfactory agro-climatic conditions for Miscanthus cultivation. On average, Miscanthus harvest yields up to 30 tons per ha at maturity with moisture content of 10-15% (considered as dry matter). However, on low quality soils the harvest yields on average are 10 t per ha of dry matter. Three scenarios based on 5%, 10% and 15% of the total abandoned land use were considered for calculating potential biomass yields based on low soil quality from this study. Table 6b shows potential Miscanthus yields based on estimation that 5%, 10% or 15% of abandoned land is used for the cultivation. Based on average pyrolysis plant requirements at 5t/h of dry base biomass, the required Miscanthus amounts would be 37 500 – 42 500 t of dry matter annually. Based on yield data, Karlovac and Sisak-Moslavina regions would have sufficient amounts of biomass considering that at least 10% of abandoned agricultural land is used.

Table 6: a) Condition of agricultural areas, especially abandoned agricultural areas in Croatia (ha) for Miscanthus energy crop. The percentage of 5, 10 and 15 considers potential actual use of the available land for plantations. * displays agricultural areas ideal for Miscanthus production (Central bureau of statistics and the Corine Land Cover (CLC Croatia – CORINE land cover database for Croatia)). b) Total yield of Miscanthus (t dry matter) based on abandoned area utilization (5, 10 or 15% respectively). Adapted from Voca et al. 2019

County	Land devoted to crops CLC (ha)	Abandoned areas (ha)			
		Total	5% areas	10% areas	15% areas
Bjelovarsko-Bilogora	106,811	20,935	1,047	2,093	3,140
Brod-Posavina	90,179	17,334	866	1,733	2,600
Dubrovnik-Neretva	19,071	19,768	988	1,976	2,965
City of Zagreb	16,470	5,467	273	546	820
Istria	35,826	63,792	3,189	6,379	9,568
* Karlovac	47,545	53,273	2,663	5,273	7,990
Koprivnica-Križevci	80,591	12,839	641	1,283	1,925
Krapina-Zagorje	39,433	14,640	732	1,464	2,196
* Lika-Senj	34,175	33,299	1,664	3,329	4,994
Međimurje	41,926	6,076	303	607	911
Osijek-Baranja	235,375	23,080	1,154	2,308	3,462
Požega-Slavonia	54,780	16,336	816	1,663	2,450
Primorje-Gorski kotar	7,793	20,557	1,027	2,055	3,083
* Sisak-Moslavina	96,572	63,062	3,153	6,306	9,459
Split-Dalmatia	48,053	54,206	2,710	5,420	8,130
Šibenik-Knin	43,997	28,517	1,425	2,851	4,277
Varaždin	47,426	8,809	440	880	1,321
Vukovar-Srijem	144,826	9,770	448	897	1,345
Zadar	49,279	28,399	1,420	2,840	4,260
Zagreb	117,056	32,791	1,419	2,839	4,259

County	Yield on 5 % of abandoned areas (t)	Yield on 10 % of abandoned areas (t)	Yield on 15 % of abandoned areas (t)
Karlovac	26,637	53,273	79,910
Lika-Senj	16,650	33,300	49,950
Sisak-Moslavina	31,531	63,063	94,594

4.1.1 Virtual plant positioning

The positioning of VPL was based on a potential yield estimation using 10% of abandoned land in Croatia, Karlovac and Sisak-Moslavina regions. For a more specified VPL location we looked at industrial activity in those regions.

In Karlovac city, INA group is situated that is a major Croatian oil and gas company that is a part of MOL group (a leading Hungarian international, integrated oil and gas company). The group also has a very large oil refinery that is situated in Sisak, 60 km from Zagreb and 100 km from Karlovac. The refinery has 61 000 barrels per day capacity. By situating VPL at the proximity of this refinery an advantage of industrial symbiosis can be used. The refinery complex has 19 major processing plants and it is one of the main producers of clean fuels (gasoline and diesel blends with biocomponents) within the country.

Figure 14: VPL positioning in Croatia. The green arrow shows Sisak town and county, where a large oil refinery is situated.

4.2 Origin

Miscanthus is a bamboo-like woody stem biomass native to North India, Asia and Africa that grows up to 2.5 - 4.5 m in height. The remarkable adaptivity of this C4 crop as well as high biomass yields makes it very attractive for biomass industry. Moreover, it has been documented as most economically feasible and ecologically efficient lignocellulosic crop (Miscanthus group, 2019). Propagated by rhizomes, Miscanthus is a very disease and pest resistant crop that does not require fertile soil and requires little fertilizer.

To establish Miscanthus cultivation, it takes 3-5 years, during which the yield of the crop increases. The cultivate can be grown for at least 20 years cycle. Yield can vary based on harvest date and methods, but typically the harvest occurs in spring when the plant stems are dry and before new shoots emerge. Yields up to 25 t/ha per year have been reported onwards the third-year cycle of growth (Lewandowski et al 2000).

Figure 15: *Miscanthus giganteus* physiology. The crop can reach the height of 2.5 to 4.5 meters from the ground level.

4.3 Growing model

Miscanthus demands little maintenance once the crop is established. Rhizome propagation is a very labor-intensive way of planting crops, however once

established is has a regular growing cycle. New shoots are produced annually from underground rhizomes those develop into robust stems. By march, when the vegetation has completely dried, Miscanthus can be harvested mechanically. The moisture content of dry stems reaches 30-50% mc. The growth cycle is repeated each year. Environmental factors and the age of the crop determine the yield. Harvest can be initiated from the first year as long as the yield is higher than 5 t/ha. Once crop maturity is reached, the yield is on average 18-25 t/ha. From 1ha of land, around 25 dry tonnes of biomass can be achieved from the 4th year of harvest.

4.4 Harvesting and processing operation

Miscanthus harvest occurs similar to conventional cereal crops. Mower conditioner is used for mowing and baling the crop (Figure 16a). It is common to harvest in spring, since peak growth occurs in autumn. The weather window for harvesting in Croatia is around 30 to 40 days. Moreover, harvesting in spring optimal moisture content (dryness) as well as higher quality of biomass and higher energy content

Figure 16: Miscanthus a) harvesting process; b) baling process; c) storage of bales in the field; d) loaded trucks with bales.

can be reached. It is possible to leave the material in the field for further drying after harvest.

Miscanthus is baled either after harvest or after further field drying (Figure 16b). The bales are transported (Figure 16d) to a processing facility where they go through a bale shredder or chopper (Figure 17a, Figure 17b). Around 85% of material is suitable for further processing in respect to dryness. Therefore, if necessary the material goes through a straw dryer process too.

Figure 17: Example of Miscanthus: a) shredding with a corn shredder; b) visual image of material after shredding; c) pellet extrusion process; d) bagging of the pellets.

Since Miscanthus can pose similar challenges as straw (e.g. dust particles, small particles, not homogenous sizing, etc), it is necessary to pelletize Miscanthus biomass to reach the desired characteristics for the pyrolysis plant. A common practice is to pelletize at processing facility after shredding or chopping the bales. The pelleting lines are usually equipped with a dryer as part of the pelleting procedure as is this necessary for pellet formation. Shredded material is taken into the hammer mill, where extrusion through a die is taking place (Figure 17c). A bagging facility bags the pellets either in 15kg bags (ideal for domestic sales) (Figure 17d) or big bags (up to 1t), based on customer needs. In the pyrolysis plant scenario case, walking floor bulk truckloads can be loaded and delivered to the plant.

4.5 Miscanthus cost estimations

When it comes to bioenergy crops, the value chain consists of four major cost items: land and labor costs, capital costs and fertilizer costs. Labor cost can be defined as hectare-based cost, it consists of wages and labor input. Capital costs are all input costs, such as machinery. All costs are ha based except for fertilizer costs, which are yield based and include fertilizer prices and input. In total, capital expenditures for Miscanthus are 576 eur/ha. The cultivation is dominated by harvesting, field transport and storage (64%)⁴. The advantage of considering Miscanthus cultivation in Romania is a significantly lowered land and labor cost compared to that to Western Europe.

4.5.1 Feedstock cost estimation

Miscanthus feedstock cost estimation is displayed in Table 7. Biomass is harvested over 30 to 40 days in spring. Biomass harvest includes a shredder, connected in the front of the tractor and a baler that can bale up to 128t/ha, connected behind the tractor (350hp). As a result, cutting and baling occur simultaneously. Transport calculation is based on 25-75 km radius. Based on cost estimations of such a harvest, the total biomass production cost can be between 47-60 €/t. The guide market price for purchasing harvested Miscanthus biomass is around 75 €/t (CIF).

Table 7: Biomass production cost from field to the site within 25 km range, based on 1t/day production capacity (8 hours).

Cost factor	Action	Predicted cost
Mower conditioner	Harvesting	160 €/ha
Baler	Baling	8 €/t
Telehandler	Handling	140 €/ha
Truck with carrier	Delivery within 25-75 km radius	4-8 €/t
Storage	-	1 €/t
Total biomass production cost		47-60 €/t
Market purchase price		±75 €/t

*1 ha = 100 t of biomass

4.5.2 Pelletizing at VPL site

This scenario considers if a pelletizing facility would be set up at Sisak VPL location in Croatia instead of purchasing ready-to-use Miscanthus pellets. In this estimation, Brand 'Himel' is used as it is suitable for dry stalk material such as Miscanthus. The production steps include ball grinding, conditioning, pelleting and weighing. The system is ready to operate after training.

Pelletizing step is considered, because Miscanthus is a type of material that has small particles and pellets improve material homogeneity when using in a pyrolysis-based system. Pelletizing increases bulk density, therefore storage and transport costs are lowered. Moreover, using pellets standardizes material size and improves

⁴ De Witt, 2010

dosing, prevents contaminants entering the pyrolysis system and prevents dust explosion.

The ratio between the input material of Miscanthus is 1:1 with an assumption that dry biomass mc is 25%, therefore drying step is included (required moisture content for pelletizing is 10-15% mc). A 62 kW pelletizer can produce 6.264 tons of pellets per year, for which 6.900 t of biomass would be needed. This is a real case scenario of on-site pelletizing possibility based on a study done in Croatia. A standard pyrolysis oil plant 5t/h plant needs 44 k-tons of dry biomass per year. There are market-ready pelletizers with different capacities based on biomass needs. This can reach a very high additional investment cost within the pyrolysis plant set up. In case this scenario is to be considered within the investment dossier, the suitable pelletizer needs to be investigated.

Table 8: Pellet production cost estimation for 1 pellet plant that would produce 6.264 t/y of pellets

Pellet production cost estimation for 1 pellet plant	Cost, €
Pellet plant lease (based on 6 years with 30% down payment)	519.800
Material and energy costs	139.512,96
Fixed costs (rent, staff)	156.451,20
Total for the plant	295.964,16
Production cost (pellets per ton)	47,25
Pellet market price (average, per ton)	180

further separately. As a result, Table 8 and Table 9 are mere guideline examples of what on site pelletizing costs are as well as what functional characteristics can be achieved with a pelletizer.

Table 9: Functional characteristics of Miscanthus pellets.

Parameter	Value
Diameter	6 mm
Moisture content	6-12%
Net calorific value	18 MJ/kg
Density	600 kg/m ³
GHG emission	15.5-20.23 kg CO ₂ eq/GJ

An alternative to considering “pelletizing on site” could be “pelletizing in the field”. In this scenario, the hay that is being harvested is directly pelletized from the field, thus skipping the baling step. Self-propelling agricultural machine without the tractor attachment is used with the automatic controlled material feed through the power regulator of the pelleting press engine. It passes via the power belt to the pelleting press after the material has been crushed in the direct flow. The pellet size can be chosen by changing the die (6-12mm possibility). The pellets are transported via the pellet bucket conveyor after cooling step. In this method, up to 6t/h of pellet capacity can be reached.

Figure 18: Miscanthus harvest and pelletizing in the field, Metitron 560 technology of self-propelling harvesters.

Although it solves the logistical problems, there are, however drawbacks on field pelletizing. If the material is first baled, bales need to be suitable size for the pelletizing machine. If the pelletizing is done directly, the machine deals with wet fibres and possible contaminants, such as soil, therefore resulting in poorer pellet quality. Overall, pelletizing in the field yields are lower quality pellet with possibly higher amounts of contaminants.

To bring back the focus on the pyrolysis process and VPL needs, purchased pellets from a pellet plant or on-site pellet production capacity would yield a much better feedstock quality and purchase price (in the case with on-site pelletizer) for the process than pelletizing on field. However, the investment cost for a pelletizing installation can be very high.

5. Supply chain of Romanian corn stover

5.1 Availability

Romania is one of the largest cereal producers in Europe. Over the last years, corn production in the country has been steadily increasing and is forecasted to increase even more by 2030. In 2018, Romania had the largest production capacity of Europe (at 18.8 mil. t). In 2019, corn production capacity has reached 14.3 million tons. Although 2019 was lower than 2018, Romania remains within higher producing countries within the EU zone (2nd largest as of 2019).

Figure 19: Harvested production of corn in Romanian regions, 2017. Amounts in million tonnes, by NUTS 2 regions. Data adapted from Eurostat, GISCO 2019.

As displayed in Figure 19, Romanian corn production is spread throughout the country, but the highest producing areas are southern west (Oltenia), southern (Muntenia) and southern east regions (Dobrogea and Moldova de sud), where the production capacity is above 3.5 million tons annually. A total of 2.5-3 million ha of corn is available based on country's 10-year average, of which on average 300-450 thousand ha reside in South west, 450-550 thousand ha in south and 400-500 thousand ha in south east. To translate this to tons, this would be 1-1.5 mil. tons, 1.5-2 mil. tons and 1-2 mil. tons respectively.

Corn stover yields highly depend on harvesting techniques and timing. For instance, when the grain moisture is at a harvesting range of 20-30%, the ratio of stover to

total biomass averages 43% (dry mass). Moreover, a sustainable residue to crop removal considers that less than 50% of corn residue is removed. The moisture content of stover ranges between 58-65% and even up to 75% for the bottom part of the stalk during the harvest. The choice of chopping, wet baling or dry baling determines the harvest yields of stover. On average, the ratio of harvested stover to total field yield (dry mass) is at 53% for chopping technique, while wet baling yields 56% and dry baling – 33% respectively. Table 10 displays corn stover availability based on these harvesting techniques and their yields. Considering that an annual pyrolysis oil feedstock use is on average 37 500 – 42 500 tones, all three regions would have sufficient corn stover available while using all harvesting techniques.

Table 10: Corn stover availability range based on corn availability and stover harvest techniques. TT – thousand tons; MT – million tons.

REGIONS	OLTENIA	MUNTENIA	SOUTH EAST
TOTAL CORN AVAILABILITY (MT)	1-1.5	1.5-2	1.0-2.0
TOTAL CORN STOVER (TT)	430-645	645-860	430-860
HARVEST BY CHOPPING (TT)	228-341	341-455	228-455
HARVEST BY WET BALING (TT)	241-361	361-482	241-482
HARVEST BY DRY BALING (TT)	142-213	213-284	143-284

Future availability based on climate change will very likely affect the amounts of corn stover available. Some simulations on climate change scenarios highlight southern and south-east Romanian regions, where drought and aridity are most likely to occur (Figure 20). This includes southern half of Oltenia, Muntenia and Eastern Dobrogea. Although to current day, the highest production fall within this area (Dolj, Teleorman counties), even with climate change northern parts of these regions will have sufficient corn stover production available. Because of management practices in Romania, a low yield potential is achieved to this date, which indicated that theoretically residue yield can be further improved by up to 30-40% (Cultivation practices, crop protection, fertilization, choice of variety, catch crop, harvest, collection, handling, storage, transport).

The main competition of corn stover in Romania is cellulosic ethanol production. For example, Sunliquid (Podari, Craiova, Dolj county), uses more than 250 kiloton of straw and stover annually. Other competitions are animal feed, however cereal residues are not well utilized to this day due to lack of upgraded technology in the country. Other competitions are biogas and energy production (e.g. heating power).

Kalizea (Slobozia, Ialomita county, Muntenia region), a leading corn processing group opened a new corn processing factory with a production capacity of 75 000 tones by 2021.

Figure 20: Regional map of Romania and predicted drought regions (highlighted in grey). *** Denote 5-6% of world production in 2010; ** 3-4% and * 2% respectively.

5.1.1 Romanian VPL positioning

In Romania, local corn stover prices average 42 eur per ton. Considering the transport with an assumption of 50-150 km range from the feedstock source, the price increases to 54-70 eur/t for non-densified feedstock⁵. Logistically, placing the pyrolysis plant nearby or between the Muntenia (Ialomița, Braila counties) and Dobrogea (Constanța county) regions (proximate to Kalizea corn processing factory) gives a good industrial symbiosis advantage, enabling the plant to be in the hub of high corn production areas and as a result plenty of corn stover availability within the recommended range of proximity. Additionally, other corn processing facilities are within proximity: AGFD Tandarei SRL (Agrana group, 36 kton corn processing capacity), Cargill silo, Constanța (unknown capacity), Bayer corn processing plant (Sinești, Ialomița County, capacity ~ 7500 ha of corn)

Moreover, by positioning the VPL more to the west, port distance can be chosen not to exceed the 150 km distance range should an export scenario need to be considered.

⁵ Prices are not considering current energy and feedstock crisis of 2022

Figure 21: Selected VPL (virtual pyrolysis plant) location area in Romania in Muntenia/Dobrogea regions. The choice was based on the large availability of corn stover from Kalizea corn processing facility (marked in green).

5.2 Origin

Widely cultivated throughout the world, corn is a domesticated crop from southern Mexico about 10,000 years ago. It is grown for various purposes, from fodder for animals, to variety human consumption needs (flour, sweet corn, popcorn, etc) including oil production, starch, alcoholic beverages, cosmetic uses, textile, paper and energy industries. Corn is a summer crop, therefore it does best when planted in late spring after the soil temperatures reach above 16 °C and it does best when the temperatures vary between 22 – 30 °C. Requiring 6-8 hours of direct sun, ideally well-drained and rich in organic matter soil with a pH 5.8 – 6.8, corn grows 1.2 – 3.6 m high and can be harvested 60-100 days after the germination, depending on the variety planted and the amount of heat received.

The farming propagation is done by seed, sowing 10 cm apart 2 seeds per hill after the land preparation with organic fertilizers. Immediate irrigation is required after sowing based on the soil type and season/weather conditions. Main diseases in corn farming are leaf spot and downy mildew. Harvesting of the corn occurs when the outer cover of the cob turns white. A good quality seed can yield up to 2.5t/ha of corn.

CORN PLANT PARTS

Figure 22: Corn plant physiology

Corn stover is considered as biomass that grows aboveground, consisting of stalks, leaves, silk, chuck, tassel and cobs, all that remain after the corn harvest (Figure 22). Like various other kinds of stover, it can be used as feed, animal bedding, direct soil amendment, bioenergy or feedstock for bioproducts (e.g. humus production).

The use of corn stover industrially presents opportunities and constraints. There is a limitation in the amount of corn stover that can be harvested when it comes to consider quality and storage of the harvest, nutrient removal and recycling, soil

carbon and quality, etc., therefore correct harvest and transportation practices, stover quality and storage and economics of stover harvest are of importance.

5.3 Harvest

Corn stover harvest occurs within a few days to a few weeks after the grain harvest. This can range anywhere from 1 October to 1 December, but the harvest window is relatively short due to spoilage and fermentation processes that depend on weather conditions and grain maturation. The harvest process involves windrowing and baling the stover. Then the bales are moved to storage sites. Once the stalks are chopped, they are windrowed, which means placing the straw in rows in specific size that will be suitable for baling. Combine windrowing can be used, where the spreaders on the back are disengaged so that the material other than grain is dropped at the back of the machinery. Commonly, this type of windrowing produces windrows of 1.85 t/ha (on average). The addition of stalk rompers or rollers on the combine header creates a more suitable windrow for baling, where less soil contaminants are brought in. If the chopper and spreader is disengaged at rear end of the combine, more stover is captured in the windrow and larger stover particles are fed more evenly when baled. By using bar rakes (rotating parallel bars) the material is conveyed into a center of the windrow and the operator has more control over the speed and flow of the material across the rake. Alternatively, wheel rakes use rotating wheels with teeth attached that sweep the stover into the center of the windrow. Rakes can produce corn stover windrows between 3-7.4 t/ha. However, it is important to point out that the yield difference is mainly due to the productivity of the crop. The material in the windrows can then be baled either in round or square bales, depending on end use. Generally, industrial corn stover production prefers large square balers. The bales are then loaded onto trucks or trailers and transported to storage facilities or processing plants.

Corn stover is typically collected from the field in Romania by hand or with mechanical equipment such as a combine harvester. The stover is collected by hand by raking or sweeping it into piles. The mechanical equipment is used to cut the stover and then gather it into piles or bales. Single pass collection has minimal soil contamination in the bales, however it is common to collect stover by second and even third pass baling. In the two-pass harvest, the grain is collected first, then the stover is baled. In this collection method corn cobs are included in the baling process. Third pass baling occurs when the stalks are shredded prior to baling, however it is not a common practice in Romania. Two pass harvesting is a common practice, while it is also considered as the most efficient harvesting technique than a three pass harvesting.

Once the stover is baled, then it is collected and loaded onto trucks or trailers and transported to storage facilities or processing plants. There are many ways to collect the bales, such as collection of the bales at the end field by using a truck mounted hydraulic bale lift table, multi-bale collection wagon drawn by a tractor or even a fork connected to a tractor (Figure 23). Collected bales are loaded onto flatbed trailers or truck beds for further transport.

Any biomass refinery prefers stover to have lowest level possible of contaminants, such as dirt or stones. Depending on the harvesting mechanism, ash content can vary between 7 and 10%. Traditional harvesting methods tend to yield higher ash content than newer chopping and windrowing equipment designed for industrial

scale harvesting and processing. Ash content up to 7% is considered as structural ash that is naturally found in the stover material.

Figure 23: Examples of bale collecting methods: a) hydraulic bale lift table; b) pull behind bale collection; c) bale fork; d) multi-bale collection wagon.

5.4 Processing

Figure 24: a) Example of tub-grinding process of corn stover bale; b) roll press compactor.

Processing of corn stover occurs throughout the year with mobile units moving from site to site at the local storage facility. A good storage facility usually has good road access and good drainage. Stover can be stored under a roof to keep rainfall off, or alternatively a tarp is placed on the top layer of the bales to be able to store them outside. Outside storage is more suitable for round bales, however corn

stover does not reliably shed water unlike the other grasses stored in round bales due to loose hatch formation.

For the industrial biomass use, this is not a viable solution since humidity of the feedstock is of importance. To minimize surface water flow into the bale stack, tarped storage is used. It involves in covering the top layer of bales with UV resistant polyethylene fabric. This way, the loss is minimized both from UV damage and rain events. The storage stacks can be stored not only at the production field, but also at satellite storage facility or centrally at the biorefinery. Permanent structure storage improves the quality of biomass by offering more storage protection. Naturally present ventilation allows the stack to lose moisture during the heating phase of biomass storage. A permanent structure requires higher initial investment cost, therefore resulting in better quality but more expensive biomass.

Table 11: Comparison of baled and chopped corn stover logistics. Adapted from Wendt 2018, Ecofys 2013,

Logistics supply chain	Bale logistics (30%wt)	Chopped logistics
Harvest and collection		
Schedule	30 day period, fall 6 days/week x 14h/day	92 day period, fall 5 days/week x 16h/day
Equipment pass 1	Grain harvester, stover comes out in a windrow behind the combine	
Equipment pass 2	A baler picks up the stover and bales it (30% of the stover is picked up)	Forage harvester with chopping head tended by tractor with high dump wagon to collect the material to semi-trucks
Format	Big round or rectangular bales	Chopped material
Density	192 kg/m ³	73.7 kg/m ³
Yield	2.7 t/ha	2.7 t/ha
Moisture content (wb)	30%	45%
Preprocessing and storage		
Operations	Receiving, two stage size reduction with hammer mills, rotary drying, conveyance	Receiving, screening, shredding, pile formation, reclaiming, conveyance
Storage	Field-side storage, bale stacks	Industrial/semi-industrial scale ensiling, piles
Weather protection	Tarped covering	Drainage system
Dry matter loss (storage)	12%	5%
Stored material density	192 kg/m ³	192 kg/m ³
Transportation		
Equipment	Flatbed truck (102 m ³)	Open top possum belly trailers (113 m ³) pulled by day cab semi-trucks (450 hp)
Handling operations	Loading, trucking, unloading, conveyance	

The bales are usually converted to bulk material by tub-grinding and roll press compacting, therefore achieving about 25-ton truck loads between 240-360 kg/m³ density to an end user.

A pellet mill is used to produce high-density pellets by a flat die or a ring die mill. In order to pelletize, corn stover is ground to 0.18-0.3 mm. The steam is used to soften the biomass and entrain the lignin. The final product is extruded and can range in 25-40 mm width and 6-12 mm length. The bulk density can be reached between 1100-1300 kg/m³.

5.5 Cost estimations

There are a number of ways to determine the value of harvested corn stover. The feed value of stover differs from industrial stover. The determined offering price is affected by a number of variables, such as who is harvesting, by what harvesting techniques, harvest yields, and also transport and storage practices, including fuel and labor cost, etc. Corn stover harvest cost can range anywhere from 30 – 90 eur/t, with the median of 60-70 eur/t dw for non-densified corn stover. The number of tons harvested per ha also influences corn stover price. Weather conditions can influence not only harvesting times of stover, but also the price. If the fall is too wet, the stover harvest does not occur until the weather conditions allow it to happen. Therefore, quality and quantity of harvested feedstock influences the price, as well as demand.

*Table 12: Techno-economic assessment of corn stover harvesting ton dry mass per ha. * including equipment amortization; ** Internal rate of return. Adapted from EU database.*

Indicators	Yield of corn by-products t dry matter (dm)/ha		
	2.3	3.5	5.0
Productivity of biomass harvesting	3920	4802	5880
Capital costs (eur)	270 000	280 000	292 000
Operating costs (eur/y)	434 000	463 000	500 000
Loan (share of the capital costs, %)		60	
Loan rate, %		7	
Net costs of the biomass bales, eur*	18	15.5	13.5
Sale price of the biomass eur		30-90	
Simple payback period, yr	6	4.7	3.7
Discounted payback period (7% discount rate), yr	7.8	5.5	4.2
IRR* %	14.5	24.1	35.5

Romania is catching up with farming techniques, therefore in the coming decade corn production is likely to expand. Increasing crop yields also mean increase in residual material. Prediction models see potential growth up to 25-30% compared to other EU regions, where increasing crop yields between 1.5 t/ha and 2.3 t/ha resulting in yields up to 7-9 t/ha.

Table 12 displays a techno-economic assessment for different corn harvesting yields. Total production cost (TPC) estimation is a total of direct and indirect production costs including fixed charges and overhead costs). Deduction of equipment amortization is also included. The payback period is 4.2 years when corn stover yields are 5 t d.m./ha. If average harvesting volumes are achieved, (3.5 t d.m./ha) the payback of the harvesting unit is 5.5 years. The payback increases to 7.8 years when the harvesting yield is 2.3 t d.m./ha.

6. Supply chain of Greek Olive kernel wood

6.1 Availability

Greece is a third highest olive producer in the world. On average, 350 000 tonnes of olive oil is produced from more than 132 million trees. Around 30% of olive production capacity lays in Crete, 26% in Peloponissos, 10% in Ionian islands (Adriatic sea), 10% in Aegean islands (Lesvos) and the rest 24% is scattered

a)

b)

Figure 25: Greece – a) Olive oil production areas; b) Distribution of olive cultivation by region. Adapted from MORE project.

throughout the country. The average production of olive groves varies from 160 to 360 kg/ha. Particular areas of Crete reach the production peak of 500kg/ha.

Greece has 35 olive pomace extraction plants, of which 11 reside in Crete (31% of the total Greek olive pomace industries) and 10 in Peloponissos (28% respectively). Typically, oil refineries buy virgin pomace from small olive cooperatives and mills that is then extracted and used for their own energy needs. Majority of olive mills within the country (80%) use a 3-phase extraction (extraction with water addition) which yields pomace with 45-60% moisture content. The virgin pomace contains approximately 5% oil and 65% waste pomace that includes olive kernels (therefore called olive kernel wood). Average heating value of dry pomace (with pit/stone, average m.c. for dry is considered 12-13%) is 3500-4000 kcal/kg, while the pit/stone (if separated in the process) yields 4500 kcal/kg. As a comparison, heating value of coal is around 4498 kcal/kg. However, olive pits in Greece historically are not extracted (separated) because of the higher costs and the technology required. Currently, (as of 2018 data) out of total olive kernel wood produced, 43% is consumed in the plant and the remaining 57% is sold.

Figure 26: Map of the Greek island Crete, displaying the regions of the island.

Table 13: Production of waste pomace (olive kernel wood) in Crete regions.

Region	Olive Kernel Wood (tn/ year)
Chania	32,110
Rethymnon	13,890
Heraklion	16,766
Lasithi	16,272
TOTAL	109,038

In Crete, Olive trees are extensively cultivated, where an annual production of waste pomace (also called olive kernel wood) on average reaches 110 000 tones (DW). Table 13 displays the distribution of olive kernel wood production by region in Crete. Currently, their waste pomace is mainly used to heat water, heat generation in houses and greenhouses as well as small industrial drying processes. Fuel uses for this feedstock are mainly exports to other EU countries in small quantities. Oil processing plants operate seasonally from November to April.

Considering that an annual pyrolysis oil plant feedstock use is on average 37 500 – 42 500 tones dm (dry matter), a combination of these island regions would serve sufficient quantities of olive kernel wood for a pyrolysis plant running at 5t/h capacity. Overall, a total availability volume of up to 62 150 tonnes annually is available within the sustainable distance⁶.

6.1.1 Virtual plant positioning

In section 6.1 where olive kernel wood availability was reviewed a decision was taken to position the VPL in Crete. This way sufficient availability of olive pomace extraction plants can be ensured within a sustainable distance of 150 km range, since many olive producers and processing facilities are small family owned businesses.

The length of the island is 260 km, which means that by situating the virtual pyrolysis oil for e.g. in the middle of the island (e.g. Kapariana) would mean that all regions and largest pomace producing factories are available within less than 150 km range. In Chania region, a pomace plant "ABEA" (Porti, Municipality of Keramia, Chania, Crete) is an important player as well as a smaller family run business "Giannoulis" (Chania, Chania). A large pomace producing company is situated in Ierapetra – Pirineleourgio Almpantaki Ierapetras LTD. Moreover, by choice to situate a virtual pyrolysis plant in the middle, Heraklion airport and largest port Knossos Heraklion are within small proximity.

6.2 Origin

Olive trees in Crete have been cultivated since 35th century BC. To this date, olive trees are more than 2000 years old and some are even above 4000 years old and marked as monumental. More than 30 million trees grow in the island, they perform well due to subtropical climate that gives long and dry summers. The olive trees are spaced either at close (5 x 5 meters) or up to distant (10 x 10 meters) distance apart due to soil type, geography (plateau or hill) and climate specifications. Cretan olive oil is known for its purity, low acidity and low peroxides.

⁶ Sustainable distance is defined as being between 50 and 150 km range.

Figure 27: Olive harvesting by mechanical harvesters (adapted from Kadmec).

Olive farming in Crete is mainly organic and heavily regulated by IFOAM (International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements). As a result, the farming is semi-intensive practice relying on weed and pruning composting, green manure, using plants for pest control (most commonly Fabaceae species, naturally growing, e.g. *V. sativa*) and livestock farming. Soil cultivation by using small tractors usually occurs after harvest promote new root growth and destroy weeds. Although traditionally not irrigated, some supplemental irrigation by drip system is present in some Cretan plantations.

6.3 Production process

During the months of November to January, Crete is in full swing of olive harvest. Despite that this is the rainiest season in the island, harvesting occurs during the dry moments as it is crucial for the quality of olive oil. Mechanical harvesters called vibrating combs are mostly used that can be operated by a single man (Figure 27) due to their efficiency. Linen or plastic sacs collect the olives and debris. Since majority of the plantations are family run businesses, it is common that all the family members contribute and help in the harvest. The olives are stowed in bags and are directly taken into the mill.

Figure 28: a) Fruit elevator to remove debris; b) olive wash process; c) malaxation process; d) centrifugation process to separate the oil; e) gravitational separation of the oil.

In the mill, the olives are transported through elevator, where the leaves and stems are removed and washed with water to remove any dirt (Figure 28a, b). The malaxation process crushes olives to paste that is mixed to allow oil agglomeration (Figure 28c). The olive paste (pomace) and formed oil is removed by centrifugation by three phase calibration (oil, water and solid separation) (Figure 28d). At this stage water addition is possible to facilitate the process. The phases separate due to their difference in density. The oil phase is a cloudy substance that later undergoes final gravitational separation (Figure 28e).

Olive oil production process produces high amounts of solid waste (kernel wood) and waste water, both containing high amounts of inorganic constituents, phytotoxic phenolic compounds. As a result, safe disposal or reuse of olive oil production waste remains a critical topic in Crete because it creates odor problems via ammonia leaching both into the ground and air.

a)

b)

Figure 29: a) Olive processing chain to olive kernel wood; b) Power generation of olive kernel wood in Crete

Olive fruit has between 12-30% oil content, which means nearly 75% of it is waste. To produce 1 kg of olive oil 4-8 kg of olives are needed. The residue from the olive oil pressing contains crushed olive pits, olive pulp, olive husk, waste water and some pomace oil. This is called olive kernel wood. Depending on the amount of water added during oil extraction, the olive kernel wood can have moisture anywhere between 40 to 70% mc, therefore drying and olive kernel oil extraction is necessary. In the pomace plant, the drying process of the olive kernel wood can achieve around 12% mc final dryness. Because most pomace plants are small plants scattered throughout the island, the drawback seen is potential chemical composition variability in olive kernel wood that can be affected by: a) harvesting practices; b) processing practices; c) drying practices. General chemical composition guideline with displayed chemical composition variation is provided in Table 14.

Table 14: Chemical composition of olive kernel wood and its variation between different research sources. Sources: Gomex-munoz et al 2012, Selami et al 2008, Albuquerque et al 2007,

Chemical composition	Value (min-mean-max)
Total C (g kg ⁻¹)	184 – 307 – 390
Total N (g kg ⁻¹)	10.7 – 15.0 – 20.0
C:N ratio	10.5 – 21.9 – 35.8
Total P %	0.2 – 0.4 – 1.2
Total K %	1.1 – 1.7 – 2.4
Organic C	1.6 – 16.5 – 25.0
Organic matter (g kg ⁻¹)	272 – 605 – 879
Particle size >1mm < 5mm	72% – 90%
Ash content	3.5 – 3.97 – 4.5

It has been reported by Vourdoubas, 2008 and Karkania 2012 that chemical composition of olive kernel wood specifically from Crete does not qualify for the production of premium quality wood pellets. Moreover, the pellet market in Greece is not so well developed, although the market growth potential is high. Olive kernel wood can be dried to around 12% mc and it does not have too many fine particles, therefore its use directly in the pyrolysis plant is possible. Therefore, pelletizing process is not considered in this supply chain.

6.4 Realistic scenario for olive kernel wood

In reality the olive kernel wood case in Greece will be very challenging as small olive owners are using the olive kernel wood for their own heating needs. In current energy market situation this challenge becomes even more prominent as small businesses will prefer to use it for their own heating needs rather than selling it. Moreover, to current date olive kernel wood covers around 8.5% of the energy needs of Crete. Because it has relatively high heating value (4,051 kcal/kg or 16.96 MJ/kg) and low price (0.15 €/kg), olive kernel wood is a favorable energy source locally. Although total availability is estimated at 110 tonnes/y, up to 62 000 tonnes/y of olive KW would be available, if not less, therefore it is possible that additional olive KW would need to be secured in this scenario. In 2021, olive kernel wood could be bought for 50-90 eur/t.

Because olive kernel wood is in granular form, flatbed trucks can be used for transport to the pyrolysis plant. The density of the feedstock is around 650 kg/m³, when dried to around 10-12% moisture content. A 60 cubic meter flatbed truck can be used to load maximally 18 – 25 thousand tonnes for transportation.

7. Feedstock suitability

In this section, the expected impact on FPBO properties is presented for softwood, olive processing residues (olive kernel wood that includes pits and pomace), miscanthus and corn stover.

To consider biomass suitability, different parameters have been looked into. A guideline moisture content of each feedstock on wet basis is presented in Figure 30. A typical moisture content is presented on wet basis based on data and practical CAPAX experience, where a typical softwood residue MC can range around 35-55% and in certain situations even above (e.g. wet winter harvesting conditions). Olive kernel wood average MC ranges between 12-30% depending on processing type (e.g. 2 or 3 phase) and other variables. For Miscanthus, a common average MC range is 30-50%, while corn stover can vary between 25-47% also depending on harvesting choices, storage, etc.

Category	Feedstock	Typical MC range, % ¹
Forest residues	Softwood residues (shavings, dust)	35-55
Organic waste residues	Olive kernel wood	12-30
Dedicated Lignocellulosic biomass crop	Miscanthus	30-50
Agricultural residues	Corn stover	25-47

¹ Values on wet basis, %

Figure 30: A guideline of moisture content range shown for each selected feedstock.

In general, different biomass feed specifications are required when compared to established biomass conversion technologies. For instance, the physical characteristics and composition of lignocellulosic biomass (ash, water, etc.) are more important parameters than a small difference in the lignin/cellulose/hemicellulose ratio.

Pre-treatment of lignocellulosic biomass plays an important role in the fast pyrolysis process and therefore suitability. For example, it can have a large influence on the yield and quality of the end product. By pre-treating biomass, the structure is modified to an extent where a suitable feedstock contains smaller quantities of undesirable components that could interfere in fast pyrolysis processing (e.g. sand, particle size, water). Depending on the type and nature of biomass, different pre-treatment mechanisms can be used. There are always limitations to each feedstock and how it can be pre-treated.

Biomass particle size plays a huge role in the suitability of biomass. It is important, that the particle size is not too small or too large. A too small particle can result in dust in the FPBO product and a too large particle will give longer residence time of the particle in the reactor, resulting in the increased production char and/or gaseous products. Preferably the biomass particle size should be in the range of 1-10 mm.

As a result, careful selection and evaluation of feedstock is necessary to maximize the FPBO yield. Table 15 and Table 16 displays chemical analysis for selected feedstocks in relation to the impact for FPBO production. The yield of the oil as a result varies feedstock to feedstock, but also due to the above-mentioned parameters. Overall, a higher nitrogen content of the residue streams will likely

increase the nitrogen content in the pyrolysis oil, which in turn could lead to increased NO_x formation thus requiring a (more extensive) gas cleaning system. Based on research data, olive kernel wood and Miscanthus is more likely to cause that, however based on real gathered data by BTG these feedstocks had much lower N ratios.

Table 15: Chemical analysis of selected feedstocks based on FPBO production data (BTG²) and Research (R¹). Most important values are displayed in order to evaluate the expected impact on the FPBO properties for each feedstock.

	Softwood dust		Olive residue		Miscanthus		Corn stover	
	BTG ²	R ¹	BTG ²	R ¹	BTG ²	R ¹	BTG ²	R ¹
C (wt.%) ³	49.2	51.1	52.5	48.8	45.9	53.2	-	50.7
H (wt.%) ³	6.2	5.5	6.5	6.6	6.0	6.8	-	4.9
N (wt.%) ³	0.3	0.1	0.6	1.6	0.3	1.7	-	0.6
Moisture ⁶								
AR (wt.%)	15.3	10	13.2	12	-	6.8	-	25.5
AD (wt.%)	5.6	-	5.6	-	3.3	-	2.0	-
LHV (MJ/kg) ⁷	18.2	18.4	20.0	18.9	16.4	20.9	-	18.3
Ash cont. (wt.%)	0.4	0.7	0.7	3.3	3.6	3.3	8.5	5.1
Ash MP ⁸	NM ⁹		NM ⁹	-		-	-	-
IT(°C)		1550			1150			
ST(°C)					1200			
HT(°C)					1220			
FT(°C)					1230			
Potential FPBO yield (wt%)	68 ⁴		57 ⁴		60 ⁴	62 ⁵	44 ⁴	51 ⁵

¹ Research data

² Data from BTG pyrolysis oil production

³ On dry base

⁴ Actual values, BTG

⁵ Research values

⁶ Moisture content AR: water content analysis on biomass as received, AD: water content of biomass after drying

⁷ LHV calculated on dry base

⁸ ash melting point according to D1857

⁹ No melting

The moisture content of the biomass is also very important and shouldn't be higher than 6 wt% in order to ensure a homogeneous single-phase FPBO. The moisture content of feedstock can vary significantly due to many parameters such as weather, harvesting, pre-treatment, etc. The higher moisture content of for e.g. corn-stover (25.5 wt%) on 'as received' basis will consume more energy for drying. In order to achieve the BTG feedstock requirements, the majority of biomass feedstocks will require pre-treatment. The pre-treatment steps can include chipping, grinding, milling, drying, sieving and potentially pelletizing for logistical and handling reasons. All these techniques are based on proven technologies. Some

feedstocks could need a more specific and potentially more intense pre-treatment steps in relation to their nature and origin.

Generally, densification improves mechanical and physical feedstock characteristics, increases the density, improves moisture and handling by homogenizing the properties of the feedstock. The following advantages can be achieved by using agglomerated (specifically, pelletized) material for the pyrolysis process: a) decrease of material loss; b) improved feedstock homogeneity; c) improved thermal and combustion properties; d) reduced/no change in chemical properties; e) increase of bulk density; f) reduction of fine particles, bridging and solidification; g) improvement of flowability, dosing and conveying properties; and h) decrease in dust and reduction in explosion risks.

Since the BTG process requires a moisture content below 6 wt%, this can only be guaranteed when pre-drying is done on site of the facility. All the lignocellulosic feedstocks are hygroscopic by nature. For some specific feedstocks, moisture contents can be guaranteed around 8-10 wt%. It needs to be noted that when feedstocks have to be refined to these specifications off site, the additional costs will be higher. Because of this it is advisable that a FPBO plant has its own pre-treatment capacity in relation to the targeted biomass feedstocks.

Table 16: Main forming ash elements in mg/kg on dry basis for each selected feedstock.

Main Ash forming elements	Softwood				
	Corn stover ¹	Branches/residual forestry	Sawmill residues	Olive kernels ²	Miscanthus
Al	60-140	0.04-0.08	8.0-14.5	410-1210	79
Ca	400-7390	0-33.3	77.5-235.0	2640-7390	1600-1790
Fe	70-680	0.9-35.0	4.2-7.3	240-800	92-120
K	8190-8500	22.5-162.4	13.1-37.1	2550-19340	3410-7200
Mg	290-500	25.3-117	0.0-7.3	353-860	300-600
Na	<50-800	0.6-23.0	0.6-1.8	46-550	31.5
Si	1100-14200	1.1-74	0.8-6.0	2270-16620	3930
Ti	70-250	- ³	- ³	11-90	4-40

¹Corn stalks contain higher amount of all elements, except for K, while corn cobs have the lowest values. ²Because of mixed nature of olive kernel wood (olive residue and stones), the variability of the elements is higher due to the presence of olive stones. ³ data not available.

The higher ash content of the residue streams will affect the pyrolysis oil yield in a negative way. Typically, a higher ash content increases the char formation, which could be used to generate additional heat and power in the pyrolysis plant. For residue streams having local usage of heat and power is even more important than for the clean softwood case.

Based on the data presented, a current speculation on the impact on FPBO properties is expected to have the lowest yield for corn stover. Olive residue and miscanthus yield is expected to be in the middle range, while softwood should be on the higher side.

8. Feedstock sustainability

Sustainability means that the needs of the present generation are met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Issues concerning greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity, carbon stock change and land use change are typically addressed in biomass sustainability schemes. In the SmartCHP project sustainability issues are assessed for five different Smart CHP supply chains by applying the European Renewable Energy Directive (REDII) emission reduction calculation methodology and other sustainability schemes. The assessment was supplemented by a check of sustainability topics that are not or only partly included in sustainability schemes but play a role in the discussion on sustainability of bioenergy. For the full assessment please refer to the Publicly available SmartCHP Deliverable D5.1 "*Sustainability assessment*".

The sustainability of the following five Smart CHP supply chains from feedstock to end-user have been assessed:

- Corn stover (Romania, East EU)
- Softwood forestry residues (Sweden, North EU)
- Olive kernel wood (Greece, South EU)
- Miscanthus (Croatia, Central EU)
- Pyrolysis oil import scenario (Netherlands, West EU)

The disaggregated emission values from biomass supply of all five Smart CHP scenarios are shown in Table 17. The highest emission value from biomass supply is observed for miscanthus. Clearly, this is due to the appointed cultivation emission values which is a consequence of being classified as energy crop.

Table 17: Summary of the GHG emissions of biomass supply of all five Smart CHP scenarios expressed in gCO₂-eq/MJ biomass

Emissions of biomass supply	Corn stover	Olive kernel wood	Miscanthus	Forestry residues	Import scenario (forestry residues)
Cultivation	0,0	0,0	4,6	0,0	0,0
Processing	0,9	0,9	0,0 ^{a)}	1,6	1,6
Sizing	1,0	0,4	1,3	1,7	1,7
Transport	0,1	0,5	0,9	1,0	1,0
Total emissions	2,0	1,8	6,8	4,3	4,3

a) Emissions of processing are included in cultivation, as the cultivation subsystem includes baling and storage on the roadside.

According to the REDII methodology, the total emissions from the use of pyrolysis oil for Combined Heat & Power application can be calculated by adding up the emissions from the extraction or cultivation of raw materials, emissions from the pyrolysis oil production process, and the emissions from pyrolysis oil transportation to end-users. The emissions expressed in gCO₂-eq/MJ are presented in Figure 31.

Figure 31: GHG emissions of the SmartCHP value chains (gCO₂-eq/MJ)

The emission reductions compared to the fossil fuel comparators as found in the RED II are presented in Table 18.

Table 18: GHG emission reduction of the SmartCHP value chains at two transport distances

Biomass type	Corn stover	Olive kernel wood	Miscanthus	Forestry residues	Import scenario
Smart CHP electricity (50 km)	95%	96%	90%	93%	91%
Smart CHP heat (50 km)	96%	97%	92%	94%	93%
Smart CHP electricity (150 km)	94%	95%	89%	92%	90%
Smart CHP heat (150 km)	96%	96%	91%	93%	92%

Results show that the emission reduction values of all Smart CHP supply chains are in the order of 89% to 97%. This indicates that the calculated GHG emission savings exceeds the required target of 70% emission reduction for electricity, heating, and cooling production from biomass fuels used in installations starting operation after 1 January 2021 and 80% for installations starting operation after 1 January 2026 as laid out in article 29(10) of the RED II. *Therefore, the energy produced from all Smart CHP supply chains can be accounted for national renewable energy targets and are eligible for financial support.*

Biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels produced from waste and residues, other than agricultural, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry residues, are required to fulfil only the greenhouse gas emissions saving criteria.

- *Residue means "a substance that is not the end product(s) that a production process directly seeks to produce; it is not a primary aim of the production process and the process has not been deliberately modified to produce it".*
- *Agricultural, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry residues' means residues that are directly generated by agriculture, aquaculture, fisheries and*

forestry and that do not include residues from related industries or processing.

Table 19 shows that only olive kernel wood as being a processing residue is exempted from the non-GHG RED II sustainability criteria. The other biomass types, i.e., corn stover, miscanthus and forestry residues (either used in Sweden or imported to the Netherlands), have also to meet the RED-II non GHG criteria.

Table 19: Overview of applicability of non-GHG RED II criteria to selected biomass types

Biomass type	Does is classify as residue following RED II?	Does is classify as agricultural, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry residues?	Biomass needs to meet the non GHG RED II sustainability criteria?
Corn stover	Yes	Yes	Yes
Olive kernel wood	Yes	No	No
Miscanthus	No	Not applicable	Yes
Forestry residues	Yes	Yes	Yes

The following conclusions and recommendations can be made from the assessment of RED non GHG sustainability criteria and the sustainability risk assessment:

- Olive kernel wood has to comply to the RED II greenhouse gas emission reduction criteria only. Corn stover, forestry residues and miscanthus need to meet the RED II non-GHG sustainability criteria as well. It is expected that all selected feedstocks are able to meet these sustainability criteria regarding e.g. soil quality and soil carbon, biodiversity and carbon stocks.
- The National Inventory Reports (NIRs), in which the carbon balance at level of countries and EU as a whole are presented, show that the European forests have a stable carbon stock. Despite these facts, in some Member States the public opinion regarding the use of forest biomass is very negative.
- All selected biomass types are included in RED II Annex IX of low Indirect Land Use (ILUC) risk biomass types, which indicates that the selected feedstocks are low ILUC risk feedstocks.
- The EU "*Guidance on cascading use of biomass with selected good practice examples on woody biomass*" did not result in the identification of sustainability risks for the selected biomass types. The production of pyrolysis oil from biomass fits in the picture that various application, from energy to chemicals and products from low value residues are possible.

Summary/Conclusion

A part of a successful small-scale CHP unit fueled with fast pyrolysis bio-oil is a successful suitable, sustainable and cost-efficient feedstock sourcing. Based on biomass feedstock analyses (price, logistics, potential for industrial symbiosis, compliance with REDII, sustainability), four feedstocks were selected based in four countries and their specific regions where sufficient availability was present:

- Sweden, Boras was chosen for its softwood residues.
- Croatia, Sisak region was chosen for Miscanthus.
- Romania, Slobozia region was chosen for corn stover.
- Greece, Crete island, Kapriana region was chosen for Olive KR (kernel wood).
- (Netherlands scenario is an export scenario, therefore it is explored in WP6)

The project aimed to analyse three feedstock/country choices, but it seemed opportune to include and look into all potential virtual plant locations identified. An entire supply chain was described for each of these feedstocks specific to the selected areas. The availability of each feedstock was evaluated locally, where a specific region was selected based on sufficient annual feedstock quantity to run a pyrolysis oil plant.

Figure 32: Virtual plant location distribution by EU regions and their chosen feedstock source.

Within the suitability analysis, chemical data for each feedstock was presented. A detailed version is available as part of deliverable 5.1 Based on this data, a conclusion was drawn that the project can expect corn stover to have the lowest yield of FPBO, while softwood should return the highest yield. Miscanthus and olive kernel wood is expected to have an average yield. The data concluded that chosen feedstocks are within sustainability considerations and GHG emissions overall exceed the EU targets required.

Within analyses, availability of each feedstock was evaluated locally, where a specific region was selected based on sufficient annual feedstock quantity to run a pyrolysis oil plant. A local cost assessment was included considering the assumption of a local plant within a 150 km range from the feedstock sourcing region/area for sustainability reasons. Table 20 displays price guideline for each feedstock locally with the exclusion to the Netherlands case.

It was concluded that VPL should be located within reach to Gothenburg port due to export scenario in Sweden. Due to this choice, Boras municipality was selected as VPL choice. Halland and Vaster Gotland regions have a lot of biomass to offer from sawmills and other wood operations within 150 reach of Boras. The price of softwood ranges from 50 to 160 eur/t (50-100 eur/t for non-densified; 120-160 eur/t for pelletized) depending on the source, humidity and other factors.

The most favorable regions for Miscanthus sourcing in Croatia are Sisak-Moslavina, and Karlovac, where an assumption of 10% abandoned land use was made in order to have sufficient biomass quantities for a pyrolysis plant. In Sisak, a large oil refinery is situated, therefore VPL was placed in that area for industrial symbiosis advantages. The local price averages ± 75 eur/t, while pelletized miscanthus price can increase to 180 eur/t.

In Romania, the decision was made to locate VPL proximate to Kalizea (Slobozia, Ialomita county, Muntenia region) plant, where industrial symbiosis is possible. On top, all high producing regions are within reach – Southern Dobrogea, Eastern Muntenia and Southern part of Moldova, where sufficient quantities of biomass are available. Corn stover price averages the most due to harvesting techniques and can range anywhere between 60-90 eur/t dw for non-densified feedstock.

In Greece, Olive production is very scattered throughout the country and majority of olive producers are small family run businesses. After availability analysis, it was found that Crete has the highest producing amount of olives, thus olive kernel wood (stones and pomace are historically not separated in Greece). Situating a VPL in the middle of Crete, Kapriana gives an advantage of having a port, airport and olive kernel wood sources within 150 km range. This way, up to 62 00 tonnes annually of olive kernel wood would be available. On average, olive kernel wood can be bought for 50-90 eur/t. However, final conclusion was made, that exploiting this feedstock is not opportune in Greece due to its primary uses (competition) and scattered availability (logistics).

Table 20: Feedstock price guide per country, eur/t. Local price represents feedstock at production gate. Delivered – considers delivery at a potential site within 50-150 km distance. Netherlands are excluded due to oil import scenario. D – Densified, for feedstock only where applicable to densify, e.g. pelletized softwood. Nd – non-densified.

Country	Feedstock	Local Price ¹	Price (nd), delivered	Price ¹ (d), delivered
Netherlands	-	-	-	-
Romania	Corn stover	42	60-90 eur/t	-
Sweden	Softwood	15-30 eur/MWh (forestry chips)	50-100 eur/t (forestry chips)	120-160 eur/MWh (pellet) or 120-160 eur/t 30-40 eur/MWh or 50-160 eur/t
Greece	Olive kernels	15 (virgin)	50-90 eur/t (dry pomace)	-
Croatia	Miscanthus	50-60	90 eur/t	-

¹ price Eur/t

Virtual Plant Location (VPL)	Feedstock	Growing\Origin	Harvesting	Transport & processing
Sweden: Västra Götaland & Halland	Forestry residues	<p>Comes from logging operations, forest thinning or improvement projects; Operations yield around 24% of hardwood residues; They can be bundles in trunks or further sized at.</p> <p>Roundwood from forestry activities is processed at the sawmill; during plank and board production by-products such as slabs can be produced;</p>	<p>Four main supply chains of harvesting exist: Terrain chipping, chipping at a landing (roadside chipping), terminal chipping, and chipping at a plant;</p> <p>Production: Varies in different sawmills; generally wood is assessed and sorted on quality and debarked in different techniques</p>	<p>Majority is transported as woodchips; on average 25-28 t\ walking floor truck; Bundling is common in Scandinavia;</p> <p>Slabs are bundled into 1 t bundles and transported with containers or flat bed trucks (25 t/truck)</p>
Croatia: Sisak-Moslavina Karlovac	Miscanthus	Full sun, many suitable soils, sufficient rainfall	Harvested annually in winter or early spring once the foliage dies from the second year of planting; Large harvest variation due to planting density, climate and soil type; The crop is cut with a mower conditioner and then baled with either large rectangular or round balers.	Flatbed trucks are used with bales weighting between 200-400 kg depending on moisture content; 25 t per truckload
Greece: Crete	Olive kernel wood	Hot, dry summers and mild cool winters	Harvested with olive harvester through late October to December;	Stones and pomace are not separated during the pressing processes. Dried in open air, transported by a walking floor truck
Romania: Muntenia (Ialomița, Braila, Buzău) Dobrogea (Constanța)	Corn stover	Grows well in warm and sunny climate with direct sunlight, moderate rain or irrigation;	Harvested in mid September-October as a dry product using hay harvesting equipment, such as a flail shredder; Stored outside in loose stacks (to facilitate drying) and eventually baled with a large round baler	Best densified before transportation due to low density (50 kg/m ³); Walking floor trucks are used; If densified, 25-28 t/truck are transported

